

MEMORANDUM

TO: The Clerk to the Committee,
Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary affairs,
Office of the Parliament,
Osu - Accra

FROM: A ■ K ■ H ■

DATE: 28th September 2021

RE: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

Introduction:

In retrospect, of events surrounding atrocities committed against humans by other humans who put themselves superior for the sheer lack of tolerance and respect for differences, some of these events we as black people or Africans have witnessed or been victims of directly and indirectly, racism or slavery; if these horrid events do not compel our sanity as Ghanaians to question this bill that seeks to dehumanize a minority for the sheer reason of a truth it claims it does not resonate with, then this great nation would fail, if it has not already, on keeping its promise on freedom and justice.

Supporting Argument:

This bill, in its opening statements, cites various institutions who have stood by its mission to oppress the LGBTTQQAAP+. It insinuates that the minority group; its activities and persons are un-African or un-Ghanaian, conveniently disregarding literature like 'Boy-Wives and Female Husbands' among other historic sources that give proof of the validity of Homosexuality and its variants in Africa, including Ghana, in precolonial and our post-colonial times. Sadly, it is the borrowed religions, more appropriately un-African religions, that this bill calls as its strong reinforcement. They have been the same ones used in the past to oppress people of the African race, considered monkeys for the sheer melanin in our skin and therefore treated as slaves, and less than animals. And while we do not need to be animals to stand for animal rights, because it is universally understood that they are sentient beings too, it is shocking that these religions are the same ones being used to discriminate, classify and eventually segregate 'proper humans' from the 'improper or sub-humans', if it even considers the born or made Ghanaian members of LGBTTQQAAP+ humans at all.

A bill that seeks to police the freedom of speech and association of a group whose intentions do not threaten public health, order and safety, is one that undermines the sovereignty of Ghana and its constitution that enforces us to practice democracy. The LGBTTQQAAP+ seeks to provide its members and allies with namely,

- a. Protection against hate crimes
- b. Asylum
- c. HIV/AIDS Awareness
- d. Access to sexual and reproductive health information as it pertains to the community
- e. Information on human rights and legal matters
- f. Information on how to be law-abiding citizens even as an oppressed minority group

A bill that cleverly uses unconstitutional vigilantism to witch-hunt persons suspected of being members of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ and even allies is one that calls for anarchy. This bill is suspicious of an agenda to destabilize the peace and security Ghana has boasted of since Independence. Division over Africa's own differences, tribal and political, is how we were conquered and needed independence. Mental enslavement and social conditioning of our race with hate propagated through religions of capitalism and whitewashed history is why Africa still stands on wobbly legs. A bill with such magnitude of hate that pitches one individual against the other, causes a blow to our stability and heaven knows that the foreign powers that be are waiting to tear this country to shreds and they can easily do so with their resources when this country and its people are blindsided by something as frivolous, irrational, and irrelevant as 'which human being deserves human rights?' when we are all human and must be treated equally and with respect.

"The bill simultaneously extends opportunities for medical and psychological support to affected persons to take advantage of those opportunities and to facilitate their integration into the larger society." This bill bites itself with this statement after insinuating that people of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ are misfits of society and yet hints on the fact that there is a smaller society, one that members of this minority probably belong to, thereby endorsing our humanity, national identity and our inherent need to belong. While the bill quickly concludes that being LGBTTTQQAAP+ is a disease, there is no conclusive scientific evidence, be it psychological or physical science, to validate this claim and so the said help that this bill seeks to provide, which it states as conversion therapy, is not backed with science or logic, but rather a belief in a higher power or deities, which people of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ community may or may not identify with. This leaves room for infringement on the freedom of association. And where unapproved (Not internationally recognized and accepted) scientific methods are applied, where we leave human lives at the mercy of trial and error, a fate similar or worse than the use of archaic Electroconvulsive Therapy and barbaric Lobotomy will render once productive people now truly mentally challenged, dehumanized, unfit and burdensome for the already paralyzed mental health institutions and the healthcare system of Ghana in general.

Proposed Interventions:

1. An immediate vote against this hate bill.
2. Access to inclusive proper sexual and reproductive health centers.

3. No interference with the innocent operations of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ Ghana community and a reopening of its Advocacy Centre.
4. Open dialogue between parliament, sexual and reproductive health professionals and the LGBTTTQQAAP+ community.
5. Prosecution of persons who physically and/or verbally abuse and assault members of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ community.
6. An action call for respect of the constitutional rights and freedoms of members of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ community as citizens of the Republic of Ghana.

Conclusion:

Inasmuch as Ghana often prides itself with keeping tradition, culture and values passed on from generations, the beloved 'Odo Ahoma So' a renown sexually explicit heterosexual television program championed by Akumaa Mama Zimbi, goes to show that we are evolving as a people and as humans, and Ghana is not a monolithic culture and the subject of gender, sex and sexuality is diverse. Left to the interpretation of "carnal knowledge", educative shows like this would be criminal as they include promotion of sexual activities other than vaginal and penile intercourse. The manner in which sane and consenting adults decide to express their identity, love and their sexual urges in the confines of their privacy should be nobody's business except a pervert's. People of the LGBTTTQQAAP+ and their allies are human and by international law, must have equality and freedom to live and love just like everybody else no matter the differences. Unless this bill can prove that members of this minority are insane, not human and not Ghanaian, all it is doing now is brewing hate and we have seen the consequences of hate in surrounding countries that treat its law-abiding citizens as less than human. This bill has a phobia. And it is the fear of the unknown. While holding on to traditions, empathy and sympathy are also values that should guide us to understanding the new things that nature in its wisdom brings. And LGBTTTQQAAP+ is as old as the history of mankind. The more reason to embrace than just tolerate. Freedom and Justice must work for all Ghanaians and all of humanity. They are our inherent rights for being born biologically human.